

FORMS, METHODS, AND MEANS OF DEVELOPING RESEARCH ACTIVITY THROUGH THE FORMATION OF THE IDEA OF ACADEMIC FREEDOM IN STUDENTS' CONSCIOUSNESS

Khudayberganov Shukhrat Shavkat o'g'li-Urganch

State Pedagogical Institute is the head of the Master's Department.

Professor of the Department of Preschool Education, Doctor of Philosophy
in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

(Khorezm region, Urganch city, +99 897 792-19-09)

sh.xudayberganov.urdpi.2025@gmail.com

ORCID-0009-0007-9006-8998

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Abstract:

In this article, specific requirements for pedagogical technologies to achieve the idea of academic freedom are analyzed in detail. Academic freedom is essentially liberal democratic views, their connection with education and training, pedagogical research is revealed. Also, the formation of university education pedagogy of higher education, which is sharply different from school and preschool education, is subject (professor, teacher, educator) and object (student, pupil, detailed information about the construction of the relationship between the student (student) into dialogue, trust in each other, the pedtechnology of encouraging the object to work on itself, to create new things is given.

Keywords: pedagogical research, academic freedom, educational process, new approach, method, qualified specialist, pedagogical problem, financial independence, liberal democratic views, continuous education, pedtechnology

INTRODUCTION. During the years of independence, a dialectically interconnected process has taken place in Uzbek ethnopedagogy. On the one hand, the process of nationalizing education was carried out on the basis of historical-pedagogical experiences and the spiritual and moral upbringing methods of the Uzbek people. On the other hand, relying on advanced international practices, pedagogical ideas, and models, Uzbek pedagogy has been enriched with new approaches, methods, and pedagogical technologies, while the process of internationalizing education in accordance with global educational requirements has also been realized.

Such a paradigmatic renewal of Uzbek ethnopedagogy, under the influence of internal and external factors, became an objective necessity. The scientific-pedagogical, national-educational, spiritual, as well as organizational and legal aspects of this renewal have been sufficiently elaborated in the research works of prominent pedagogical scholars of the Republic, including S.Rajabov, R.Kh.Jo'rayev, B.Qodirov, M.Ochilov, O.Kh.Fayzullayev, R.Mavlonova, K.Hoshimov, Z.Mirtursunov, X.Xurramov, M.Mirqosimov, O.Musurmonova, K.Zaripov, S.Ochil, S.Hasanov, K.Qosimova, Sh.Otajanov, and X.Ziyomuhamedov.[3].

The analysis of their scientific and pedagogical views and experiences does not fall within the scope of our study; however, it is precisely these scholars who have made a significant contribution to securing a stable place in Uzbek pedagogy for the study of enriching ethnopedagogical heritage and national traditions of the independence period with modern pedagogical technologies, as well as for investigating the innovative socio-didactic and ontogenetic foundations of forming a harmoniously developed generation, both physically and intellectually mature.

Owing to their scholarly efforts, the idea that the effective use of national upbringing and ethnopedagogical experience constitutes one of the most efficient means of fostering a well-rounded generation has been firmly established in Uzbek pedagogy as a paradigmatic concept.

MATERIAL AND METHODS.

At present, a number of scientific studies are being conducted on the formation of the idea of academic freedom in the consciousness of students. In this regard, research works aimed at developing the concept of academic freedom in students'

consciousness through modern didactic support tools have been examined.

In studying the problem, the concepts of academic freedom and financial autonomy applied in foreign higher education institutions, along with their methods of implementation, approaches, criteria, and stages, have served as a conceptual framework.

RESULTS AND THEIR ANALYSIS. The paradigm ideas mentioned above were also relied upon in the adoption of the Republic of Uzbekistan's "Law on Education" (1997) and the National Program for Personnel Training (1997). At the same time, according to experts' analyses, several issues characterized higher education institutions at that time: first, the existing system for admitting teachers to higher education institutions was inefficient; second, there was no sufficient intellectual reserve to provide higher education institutions, particularly their branches, with qualified academic and pedagogical staff; third, the lack of concentration of scientific and pedagogical personnel hindered the development of innovative knowledge; fourth, the material and technical base of higher education institutions, including laboratories and specialized teaching staff, was often inadequate or absent, yet almost all institutions were permitted to train specialists across various fields; fifth, the quality of school graduates was not high, and even state higher education institutions did not meet the required student standards; sixth, the educational programs at higher education institutions had not been optimized in terms of content and structure. [4].

The views expressed by R. Xolmuradov-Rector of Samarkand State University, Professor, Honored Scientist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and member of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis-may be subject to debate; however, they are clearly aimed at improving the effectiveness of higher education institutions through a critical assessment of their activities.

For instance, while taking pride in the fact that international experts recognize the literacy rate of the population as exceeding 96 percent, insufficient attention was paid to the need to strengthen the material and technical base of higher education institutions, to equip them with modern laboratories, and to review curricula by reducing subjects not directly related to professional training.

Educational processes in higher education institutions were conducted within strictly regulated state requirements, and the participation of professors and instructors in foreign university grants or the invitation of foreign specialists was placed under strict control. Moreover, various pretexts and restrictions were devised to gradually exclude retired professors from higher education institutions.

However, the processes of globalization and economic integration, along with the growing demand for modern кадров (qualified personnel) and education, stimulated the establishment of new higher education institutions in cooperation with Uzbekistan on the basis of international agreements and treaties. One such institution is INHA University in Tashkent, founded in 2014, which has become a symbol of cooperation between the higher education systems of Korea and Uzbekistan.

INHA University in Tashkent, established in Tashkent, provides higher education and training for specialists in the field of information technology in Uzbekistan. This higher education institution, which focuses on training personnel in digital technologies, hosts a number of advanced infrastructures, including the "Center for Supporting Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas, and Technologies" LLC, a data center operating in accordance with the TIER II standard, facilities for hosting and colocation services, the INHA University Incubation Center in Tashkent, the Co-learning Center for working with gifted students, engineering laboratories, and innovative engineering centers meeting international standards, such as Oracle, SAP, Cisco, AKFA Group, Artel Electronics, and PSB Bank.

The dynamics of IT education demonstrate steady year-by-year growth. According to available sources, while the number of IT centers in Uzbekistan was only 8 in 2019, today their number exceeds 205, and further growth is projected in the future. In the structure of high-demand professions, IT specialists rank second (12.1%) after trade sector employees (14.7%). Globally, more than 53 million students and approximately 1.7 million teachers utilize information technology in the teaching of informatics.

Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) in the field of information technology possesses significant export potential, with its global market volume amounting to approximately 3.5 trillion US dollars. In order to secure a position in this market, Uzbekistan is establishing BPO training schools within IT parks.

At the same time, experts emphasize that there is a shortage of IT personnel in Uzbekistan, and the demand for such specialists is expected to increase in the coming years. To address this issue, it is necessary to further develop high-quality online education and to introduce internationally recognized educational platforms such as Coursera, Skillbox, and Udemy. Furthermore, the development of IT educational content in the Uzbek language is of particular importance, as it will facilitate the integration of Uzbek youth-who often encounter difficulties in learning English-into advanced innovative educational systems[5].

On October 9, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "On the Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was promulgated. This conceptual document establishes more than 70 target indicators aimed at developing public-private partnerships in higher education, establishing branches of higher education institutions in order to promote regional development, increasing higher education coverage to 50%, and introducing advanced foreign teaching methods, pedagogical technologies, as well as modern management and marketing practices to improve the international rankings of Uzbek higher education institutions.

One of the key priorities outlined in the document is the integration of higher education with production, practice, and business requirements. International experience demonstrates that precisely such integration has transformed higher education institutions into leading research centers characterized by academic freedom and financial autonomy. For instance, according to O. Nayimov, a Fulbright Program researcher at Kent State University and Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Political Science, aligning higher education with business needs has enabled universities to become "leading research and intellectual centers."

A number of factors contribute to ensuring the quality and sustainability of scientific research. These include genuine academic autonomy, critical thinking, freedom of expression, strong institutional foundations of universities, effective incentives for research activities, well-equipped libraries, and high technical capacity.

In research universities, the teaching workload of academic staff is significantly reduced. Based on the "2+3" model, faculty members typically teach only two classes in the first semester and three in the second semester. This allows scholars to devote the majority of their time to research activities. The professional growth of scholars as highly qualified specialists, as well as their achievement of high scientific results, largely depends on the scope and quality of the research they conduct. [6]. In addition, articles published in reputable, high-quality journals play a crucial role in evaluating the research activities and scholarly output of academics. Many journals subject each submitted article to expert peer review, with particular attention given to the scientific novelty and originality of the research presented.

In the United States, most research journals require that studies across various disciplines undergo review by universities' Institutional Review Board (IRB). This process ensures that the research complies with ethical and academic standards, including the absence

of plagiarism and adherence to established research protocols.

From this perspective, it is noteworthy that the federal government of the United States mandates the functioning of Institutional Review Boards in all universities. [6].

Since January 2023, the establishment of such collegiate councils has also begun in 36 higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Republic of Uzbekistan, following the principles of academic governance. This initiative is supported by the normative framework of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Science and Scientific Activity" (October 29, 2019) and the Law "On Innovation Activity" (July 24, 2020). These legal instruments emphasize the critical role of universities and research centers in advancing the Republic's innovation and industrial development. They call for the adoption of best practices from leading international universities, integration of teaching and research processes, the creation of collegiate councils, and the provision of the necessary conditions for their effective functioning. Furthermore, these documents outline the monitoring of educational and pedagogical activities through such councils and the gradual development of internal university democracy.

Previously, similar functions were performed by academic councils; however, the focus has now shifted to establishing internal democratic governance within universities. This represents a paradigmatic shift for HEIs in Uzbekistan, allowing for future scenarios in which heads of departments, deans, and even rectors may be elected through open, democratic procedures. In some foreign universities, collegiate councils are granted such authority, overseeing the performance of each faculty member, including lectures and academic duties, and evaluating their fulfillment of assigned responsibilities.

The above-mentioned laws of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan set as priorities the alignment of higher education and scientific research with international standards, ensuring financial autonomy, activating intellectual potential, enhancing the scientific engagement of scholars, and supporting the achievements of talented students in research. The country's innovative development is directly linked to the academic mobility and activity of youth, the level of their scientific and technical knowledge, and the practical implementation and commercialization of such knowledge. The social, educational, and innovative significance of these objectives is further reinforced by the Presidential Decree "On Measures to Further Improve the Activities, Organization, Management, and Funding of the Academy of Sciences" (February 7, 2017) and the Decree "On Approval of the Concept for

the Development of Science until 2030" (March 9, 2020).

Additionally, as part of the national development strategy, the modernization of higher education includes implementing a credit-modular system based on international experience. Following the proposal and initiative of Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in 2020, ten HEIs were granted academic and financial autonomy. Additionally, transformation trials were conducted at five higher education institutions with the participation of foreign specialists. [9]. The Decree adopted by our President on December 24, 2021, titled "On Additional Measures to Ensure the Academic and Organizational-Administrative Autonomy of State Higher Education Institutions," recognized academic freedom as a stable reality within the higher education system, ensured its protection, and opened avenues for the effective utilization of existing scientific intellectual resources and assets. By that time, the organizational and legal framework for guaranteeing academic freedom, often discussed in various periods, had been established. Serving this fundamental purpose, 49 regulatory documents related to the modernization of higher education institutions were developed and are currently being implemented in practice.

Another paradigm shift in higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan has occurred with the emergence of international and non-state universities. In this context, Tashkent International Westminster University and Qo'qon University, established in 2019, can be cited as examples. Westminster University is the first international higher education institution established in Uzbekistan. Currently, it trains highly qualified specialists in fields such as economics, business, finance, management, information systems, and commercial law to meet international standards.

To ensure academic freedom, the university has established creative collaborations with various foreign higher education institutions. Many faculty members are members of international associations and forums, promoting our national experience. The university annually holds the "New Academic Talent" competition aimed at developing students' academic literacy and engagement.

The university has a five-year development plan, which includes:

Establishing a research culture and enhancing scientific capacity;

Promoting innovation in research and its commercialization;

Developing multidisciplinary and international collaborative research;

Improving the quality and competitiveness of scientific research.

According to Sh. Mustafakulov, Rector of Qo'qon University and Doctor of Economics, the

university provides international-level education in economics, finance, management, hotel and tourism management, foreign languages and literature, English, primary education, computer engineering, and psychology. Highly qualified academic staff from the world's leading universities have been recruited. The university is a member of the Union of Turkic Universities and develops joint programs with universities in Karelia and the United Arab Emirates. It strives for academic excellence and prepares highly skilled professionals. [6].

Academic and financial independence does not mean that higher education institutions (HEIs) can immediately be freed from state support or budgetary assistance; this is a natural reality. No matter how extensively we implement advanced foreign models, without a supportive business environment, a population capable of purchasing modern products and services, and well-developed markets, such models remain merely on paper. Evaluating educational and pedagogical processes in universities solely from a business perspective represents a one-sided approach. In our view, it is still uncertain whether universities can fully operate in accordance with market economy demands and the parameters of innovative and industrial development. Therefore, continued state budget support for universities is necessary.

According to I. Abdurahmonov, Head of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation, the private sector's share in financing science in 2022 increased almost sixfold compared to five years ago. Previously, only 8% of funding came from sectoral contributions; now it has risen to 30–40%. "This is considered a very positive indicator in global practice. Nevertheless, the majority of funds allocated to science and education still come from the state."

At the same time, our academic expert highlights initial experiments aimed at bringing the science and education system closer to practical applications and integrating it with industry. This is one of the methods to ensure academic and financial autonomy for universities. I. Abdurahmonov notes: "The private sector cannot yet be motivated to engage in science because of a shortage of qualified personnel. Only if managerial staff in our developing industries are highly qualified and appreciate the value of science and education will they confidently allocate targeted funding. Simply assigning enterprises to a specific university or research institute is insufficient. Therefore, we plan to take the first steps ourselves in the sectors. We will establish engineering schools within industries and involve students in them.

The level of academic employability in universities must increase. Each professor and teacher should have a subject that has become their personal brand. Organizational reforms are being implemented in

this regard. This will prepare applicants to study at a particular university under the guidance of a particular professor, based on their aspirations. Universities need to develop their own brand and establish their own traditions. They should serve not only as centers of knowledge but also as institutions for education and personal development. Student councils and associations encompassing various fields will be organized to support such activities within universities.”¹.

Based on international experiences, certain observations and reflections can be made.

First, modernizing higher education institutions (HEIs) and aligning educational processes with socio-regional development needs and business objectives is not an easy task. Increasing the number of HEIs naturally stimulates regional social development. However, it is necessary to carefully consider the region’s infrastructure, socio-economic characteristics, demographic situation, availability of labor resources, actual workforce conditions, the business environment, and the demand for educational services, as well as broader ethno-social needs. Without these considerations, an HEI may become dependent on the state budget, unable to generate its own financial resources, with weak personnel and insufficient scientific and pedagogical staff.

Even now, the shortage of qualified teaching staff and professors in regional branches is evident. As a result, the graduates from these institutions do not meet market requirements, and the lack of contemporary knowledge limits the impact of these HEIs on regional development. This issue was also highlighted by academic I. Abdurahmonov in the interview cited above.

For this reason, it is worth recalling the warning of Professor R. Kholmurodov, Rector of Samarkand State University, prominent Uzbek scientist, and member of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan: “In the next four to five years, the number of higher education institutions will increase excessively. However, everything must remain within reasonable limits; otherwise, the number of unemployed graduates will rise.” [9].

It is an important task to stimulate young people’s interest in acquiring knowledge, but equally pressing is ensuring that they are provided with employment in their respective fields in the future. Considering the persistent gap between the demand of the national economy for qualified personnel and the supply from higher education institutions (HEIs), we can anticipate a sharp increase in the number of

“unemployed graduates” in the future. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure cooperation between HEIs and the national economy to bridge this gap. In this regard, collaboration between HEIs and businesses, as well as entrepreneurs, plays a crucial role. Such cooperation should not be limited to one-time financial assistance but should be conducted consistently. It is advisable to implement this through preferential measures by the state and business entities supporting HEIs, such as tax incentives and other facilitation mechanisms.

Transitioning regional HEIs to operate under conditions of academic and financial autonomy also requires certain pedagogical and organizational experiments. These experiments should be based not on administrative control but on the principle of developing internal democracy within universities.

Secondly, the expansion of online education through mass media and expert engagement helps develop distance learning, which, in turn, provides opportunities for broader use of innovative information technologies in higher education. Online or distance learning expands the university’s capabilities and improves financial sustainability. Under conditions of financial autonomy, this method is very convenient. In foreign countries, this approach is used effectively, and there are graduates who have never visited the university campus but have interacted with professors solely through online classes. Such a model could also succeed in our context. Even now, in full-time education, some students attend classes irregularly, sometimes missing weeks or months, yet manage to pass the semester successfully.

Based on experience, it is necessary not to rush into innovations in education. First and foremost, an educational culture must be developed. For example, are there students ready for independent work and distance learning, and what percentage of professors and instructors are capable of delivering high-quality distance education? The most critical question is whether we have sufficient technologies to organize distance learning. Even a single deficiency can compromise educational quality.

R. Kholmurodov emphasizes: “Today, we do not need mediocre education; Uzbekistan must ensure that the intellectual potential of its population is high to maintain independence and freedom in the current geopolitical context. Education is similar to honey: if you dilute a pot of honey with water, will its sweetness remain? Of course not. Similarly, if education is treated superficially and quantitatively today, its impact on societal development will only be seen tomorrow. Therefore, along with establishing high-quality

¹ “Ғоя ортидаги синоат”. Ўзбекистон Республикаси олий таълим, фан ва инновациялар вазири, академик Иброҳим Абдурахмоновнинг “Янги Ўзбекистон” ва “Правда

Востока” газеталари бош муҳаррирларига берган интервьюси // “Янги Ўзбекистон”, 2023, 7 март

universities, we must also develop a pool of qualified professors and instructors. Currently, their number is insufficient, and many are not accustomed to working at modern standards. They lack experience in using contemporary pedagogical technologies, establishing international collaborations, publishing in foreign journals, integrating educational processes with practical and business needs, and commercializing new developments.

To address these shortcomings, it is necessary to bring into the HEI system scholars who are familiar with modern approaches and commercialization methods. Every instructor should be able to

independently secure financial resources for their subject area and seek ways to commercialize scientific developments. Academic mobility and engagement must concern the entire university community, including both teaching staff and students. This, in turn, encourages HEIs to study ethnosocial problems in their regions and conduct both scientific and applied research to develop effective solutions."

Examples of methodological and didactic recommendations were developed and implemented in practice to effectively utilize class time for shaping the idea of academic freedom in the consciousness of students and youth.

Reflexive Technology for Shaping the Idea of Academic Freedom in Students' Consciousness

Stages:	Level I	Level II	Level III	Level IV
1	2	3	4	5
Knowledge	The academic learns, knows, and remembers knowledge related to academic freedom.	Understands the essence of phenomena in relation to academic freedom and describes their characteristics	Explains the laws of manifestation of academic freedom in the lives of future educators in relation to what it reflects.	Students perceive academic freedom as a norm of life. They adopt a focus on academic freedom in their activities.
Method and Methods	Reproductive figurative conversation, incomplete speech method, and others.	Depending on the level of knowledge, oral and written questions, conditional-graphic demonstration work methods.	Problematic character conversation, thought scale, self-assessment, and others.	Project activity, manifestation of personal relationships in the activity, etc.
Academic freedom	Demonstrate a level of interest in academic freedom.	Accepting the essence of academic freedom as a socially important issue.	Analyze personal attitudes towards academic freedom, determine personal life direction.	Life principle: I act in accordance with this academic freedom.
Method and Methods	Methods for creating conditions for academic freedom.	Analysis of life experiences	Game situation, modeling, educational project, social project, observation, self-assessment methods.	
Activity Experience	Observational experiment	First experience	Adaptive experience	Knowledge and skills related to academic freedom that are reflected in real life
Methods and techniques	Working with sources,	Role-playing is a way of evaluating each other.	Working with problematic documents.	Working with problematic documents.

	empirical discussion.			
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The technology consists of four components:

Theoretical-methodological - defines the goals, objectives, and principles of developing the concept of academic freedom in students.

Content-based - outlines the concept of forming the idea of academic freedom in the consciousness of future pedagogical personnel, realized in practice through the triad: knowledge-academic freedom-activity.

Process-oriented - organizes the system of pedagogical and student activities based on reflexive methods and techniques.

Evaluative - includes indicators, levels, and criteria for assessing their success.

Thus, forming and developing the idea of academic freedom in future pedagogical personnel using modern educational technologies, their organization and implementation, and ensuring the effectiveness of the expected results is a pressing issue. Achieving this goal requires a new approach. Organizing teaching, methods, and tools based on the model described above is crucial for shaping the concept of academic freedom in students.

CONCLUSION. Academic freedom is essentially rooted in liberal-democratic principles and is closely connected with education, upbringing, and pedagogical research. University education shaped higher education pedagogy, which differs sharply from school and preschool education, and is based on a pedagogical technology that encourages dialogue between the subject (professor, teacher, educator) and the object (student, pupil, learner), mutual trust, independent work on oneself, and the creation of new knowledge.

This process did not emerge immediately; elements such as intellectual independence at universities, striving for scientific innovation, and the free organization of classes developed over centuries and were enriched with various theories and educational technologies. For long periods, methods of pedagogical pressure from family, preschool, and school systems were preserved in higher education. These methods began to change under progressive ideas and influences in the 19th century. Specifically, the pedagogical views and educational methods of R. Descartes, F. Bacon, J. Locke, J. Helvetius, J. J. Rousseau, I. G. Pestalozzi, A. Diesterweg, and J. A. Comenius gradually found expression in university education.

It can be said without rejecting the scientific-pedagogical legacy of these thinkers that the work of I. Kant on faculties is directly relevant to our topic. In the history of philosophy and higher education, Kant was the first to distinguish between religious and secular knowledge, theology and philosophy, and confirmed that the idea of freedom in university education is connected with human liberty and civil rights. Freedom in pedagogy is characterized by independence of thought; for this reason, it facilitates the emergence of free thinking methods in other disciplines. Philosophical and pedagogical reflections on academic freedom, the pursuit of guiding thought toward true knowledge, contribute to the development of science and the flourishing of freedom. [10].

Forming the concept of academic freedom among students is an important process that requires solving several key challenges.

We consider it essential to promote research activity as a means of investigating innovative teaching strategies for students. They should be encouraged to conduct small-scale research projects within their groups, reflect on the effectiveness of their learning methods, and make informed decisions based on their findings.

Highlighting the success stories of teachers who demonstrate autonomy in teaching and achieve positive outcomes in their practice is important. Presenting such examples can inspire future pedagogical personnel to develop their own academic independence and apply innovative teaching methods.

To support autonomy in teaching and learning and to ensure that future pedagogical staff have the freedom to update and adapt their educational approaches, the following strategies can be implemented:

It is necessary to create a supportive environment. Educational institutions must foster a collaborative and supportive atmosphere that values and encourages autonomy, ensuring academic freedom in teaching and learning. This can be achieved through promoting open dialogue, providing access to resources, and recognizing and implementing innovative teaching practices.

Professional development opportunities should offer future pedagogical personnel access to pedagogical innovations, instructional design, and educational technologies, providing the essential

knowledge and skills for learning new teaching methods and effectively integrating them into practice.

It is crucial to encourage the integration of technology into teaching and learning. In our view, providing training and resources for future pedagogical personnel to effectively use educational technologies and platforms is essential. By offering diverse methods for delivering technological content, facilitating student engagement, and personalizing learning experiences, academic autonomy characteristic of academic freedom can be realized.

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